

Study of the Functional Properties of Plant Protein Concentrates for Use in Fortifying Some Food Products

Qamar Mohammed Karim, Fayhaa Hatem Omran,
Zahraa Akram Hassan, Nabaa Raheem Jaber

Department of Food Health and Nutrition, College of Food Sciences, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Karim, Q.M., Omran, F.H., Hassan, Z.A., & Jaber, N.R. (2024). Study of the Functional Properties of Plant Protein Concentrates for Use in Fortifying Some Food Products. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 917-924.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).75](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).75)

Abstract:

The current study aimed to isolate and concentrate protein from flax seeds and study their chemical composition and functional properties. The process of preparing a flax seed sample was carried out by removing the gel present on the surface of the seeds, drying and cooking the sample, and removing fat from the dried sample using a Soxhlet device and using a hexane solvent to obtain stripped flax flour. Fat for the purpose of conducting the process of isolation and concentration of defatted flax flour proteins, using the method of alkaline extraction and precipitation at the electrical neutral point to collect the isolated and concentrated protein, dry it, and study its chemical composition. It was found that the protein percentage

increased to (66.58%), the ash percentage increased to (4.8%), and a decrease 1.72% respectively, and some functional properties of the protein concentrate, moisture and fat content (1.9%) of flax, were studied. The foaming property of the protein concentrate was studied and the results showed a decrease in foam formation, reaching 2%, while the stability of the foam was 100%. This was observed when the emulsification property was studied. The protein 36.66% (respectively), while the results of the characteristic, concentrate of flax has a decrease in emulsion formation and emulsion stability if it reaches (38.88% fat and water binding). Water binding is higher as it reaches (2.10 ml water/gm protein) compared to the fat binding property which reaches (1.90 ml).

Keywords: *protein, flax seed, concentrate, foam and emulsion formation.*

Introduction

Proteins are among the important components in food manufacturing and the development of food products because they are responsible for the increasing growth of the population and the decrease in resources. The various functional properties that provide acceptance by the food consumer in the world and the excessive intake of animal proteins, which are unhealthy because they contain associated saturated fats, have shown interest in research. We look for new sources of proteins from unconventional raw materials.

Vegetable proteins are among these materials and are the most abundant in the world. Many plant proteins have been introduced into food products due to their functional and nutritional properties. Oilseed proteins are rapidly gaining great importance in protein supplements due to the unique functional properties and intrinsic properties of, The degree of purification and control over manufacturing conditions are important factors, And the methods and conditions of its isolation, proteins, such as their amino acid content that affects the functional properties of food Flaxseed or linseed, known as

Linum usitatissimum L., is an annual crop grown mainly for the purposes of oil, fibre, food and fodder. The importance of this crop has increased greatly in the world. Its strong biological activity makes its use possible in various applications such as modern because of its exceptional nutritional content with... Functional foods, health supplements, and skin care products (Sanmartin, Giada and Lourdes, 2010). The importance of flax seeds has also increased recently due to the new trend of plant-based plants around the world (et al, 2022) and the number of social, ethical, religious, environmental and sustainability concerns associated with consumers all over the world. Flax seeds are becoming increasingly popular as a superfood due to their beneficial role in consuming products. Animal a b, in regulating bowel movement and alleviating the symptoms of many human diseases, such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, neurological disorders, menopause, skin problems, digestive system problems, and even (Mueed, et al. 2022). Cancer, it has recently been emphasized that flax seeds are included in the diet as an important grain due to the nutritional benefits of its components, especially, Fats, proteins, peels, and fibers, and their use in developing many value-added products (etal, 2022 Saka) Previous studies 1. Khalid et al. (2003) isolated and concentrated sesame proteins and studied the functional properties of the sesame protein concentrate and the effect of pH and salt concentration in the extraction process. It appeared that the best solubility was at pH 3 and the least solubility at pH 5. The formation and stability of the emulsion, as well as the foam and its stability, decreased at Ph 5. Close to the electrical neutralization point and high salt concentrations.2. Jasser (El) (2010) studied the chemical and biological properties of the protein of local cowpea seeds grown in the Jizan region. Alkaline extraction was used to isolate and concentrate the cowpea proteins. The protein percentage increased from 22.9% in the seeds to 77.6% in the concentrated protein, and the fat percentage decreased from 0.3 - 0.1%, carbohydrates from – 64.3 9.4% and fiber from 0.1 – 1.0%.3. Mao and Hua (2012) isolated and concentrated walnut proteins from defatted walnut flour by alkaline extraction and

electrostatic precipitation for the purpose of studying the chemical composition and functional properties of the concentrate and concentration of walnut proteins. The resulting protein percentage was good as it increased from 52.5% in defatted walnut flour to 75.6%. In walnut protein concentrate and up to 90.5% in walnut protein concentrate.4. Taha et al. (2013) used alkaline extraction and electrostatic precipitation for the purpose of isolating and concentrating sunflower proteins from sunflower meal to produce protein hydrolysates from it. The resulting percentage of protein in the concentrate was 95.1%, compared to 53.8% in the meal.5. Flores-Martinez et al. (2013) prepared a concentrate of flax seeds and studied its chemical composition and properties. The functional properties were used and the response surface method was used. The pH for dissolution was from 11-9 and the pH for extraction was 4.2-4.8. The percentage of protein increased from 26.5% to 66.0% and the functional properties improved. The aim of the research. This research aims to produce protein concentrates from flax seeds and study the functional properties of these plant protein concentrates with the aim of using them to enhance some food products. Emphasis will be placed on analyzing and evaluating the functional properties possessed by these protein concentrates, such as the ability to emulsify, foam, and absorb water and fat flax seeds abundant in 23% of the total seed weight, and these proteins constitute up to 23%It is, Flax seeds are a source of 35 to 40% of the meal after extracting the oil. Flaxseed's balanced amino acid mix gives it a high protein quality score (82%), which is better than soybean (Wu etal, 2019). Likewise, flaxseed's lysine-to-arginine ratio of 0.37 is much lower than soybean (Wu, etal. 2019). 0.88), (Figure 2) (Wu, etal. 2019). Flax seeds mainly contain two types of proteins, albumin and globulin. The basis of solubility properties, also known as lignin and choline. Globulins constitute 80% of total proteins.

Figure 1. Shows whole Flax Seeds

Beer of amino acids containing flaxseeds are a favorite source of protein because they contain amounts of... Sulfur, such as cysteine and methionine; Branched-chain amino acids, such as leucine, isoleucine, and alanine, and essential amino acids, such as tyrosine, threonine, and lysine. Flaxseeds are rich in storage proteins such as aspartic acid, glutamine, asparagine and arginine, like other seeds, which contribute to their high amide content (Wu, et al. 2019).

Amino acids	Flaxseed protein meal (g/100 g)	Flaxseed protein hydrolysate (mg/g)
Alanine	4.59	n.a *
Arginine	10.63	33.12
Asparagine	9.76	496.51
Cysteine	3.80	n.a *
Glutamic acid	26.92	911.05
Glycine	6.14	288.43
Histidine	2.45	118.63
Isoleucine	5.21	207.49
Leucine	6.82	261.79
Lysine	4.18	191.41
Methionine	2.20	104.09
Phenylalanine	5.33	284.49
Proline	5.24	n.a *

Figure 2. Shows the Amino Acid Content of Flax Seeds

Methods of protein isolation and concentration: Concentrated vegetable proteins constitute the ideal complementary materials for fortifying new types of foods. They are a good base material. Concentrated proteins are rich in total proteins and contain smaller amounts of soluble sugars, fats, and phenols. Soluble sugars and fats are undesirable compounds because they may interact with proteins through interactions and fibers. Tryptophan, methionine, and untreated fibers, result in a deficiency in essential amino acids such as allucin, which are desirable for protein production. Some studies have proven that most plant proteins reduce the risk of premature death by up to 8 percent, as plant

proteins such as legumes, whole grains, and nuts help protect against aging diseases. An increase in daily consumption by 3 percent was associated with a decrease in the risk of premature death, in addition to the fact that some people who consume plant proteins are exposed to a lower risk of death from cardiovascular disease by 12 percent. There are many methods of extraction and isolation of plant proteins: Functional properties of protein: Functional properties are defined as the comprehensive physical behavior or what the protein accomplishes in food, which reflects the interactions that occur and are affected by the structure and composition of this protein from amino acids. When polar amino

acids are increased in the protein, For foam, as for non-twisted installation molecule, the solubility of the protein increases and it is benefited from it as an emulsifying agent. And an ingredient (open) for protein chains, which works to increase the protein's ability to form a gel and the stability of the foam, even at a temperature Such as the use of high temperatures and the use of concentrated acids and bases to change the protein structure, Manufacturing: dura and organic solvents that would change the properties of functional proteins (Jasim 1983,). Functional properties are affected by several factors, including temperature, pH, protein composition, type of protein source, various treatments, ionic strength, as well as the manufacturing processes conducted with food and its general composition. In general, the functional properties of protein in food systems depend on the molecular structure of the protein, temperature and pH (Al-Taie 1986,) Emulsion property: An emulsion is a heterogeneous system consisting of at least one immiscible liquid that spreads into another liquid in the form of droplets, the diameter of which generally does not exceed 0.1 micrometer. The stability of the emulsion can be increased by adding surfactants or by the presence of Soft solids, and emulsions of fat and water can exist in two types and this depends on (W/O) and if it is the opposite, thin

at fairs on which of them it spreads into the other, then if water is spread in the fat it is called water, Fat spreads in water and is called fat in water (O/W) (Al-Taie, 1986). Foam Properties By introducing air by whisking or Foam capacity is the maximum volume that can be obtained from spreading the protein followed by Stirring or aeration. Foam stability means its ability to retain the maximum volume of air inside the formed bubbles for a certain period (Al-Taie 1986). The protein becomes unfolded. Hydrophobic areas become visible, and the internal/surface tension between air and water decreases. So when which facilitates the deformation of the liquid and the formation of An impermeable membrane would increase aeration and thus foaming in the solution would increase (Jasim, 1983). Removing the gel from the seeds: Remove the gel on the surface of the seeds by soaking the whole seeds in warm water (45°C) at a ratio of 10:1 (seeds/water) with continuous stirring using a magnetic stirrer (about 1200 rpm) for 4 hours. Then the seeds are rubbed manually. Wash twice with warm water, then dry the seeds with a cotton cloth and place them in an air- powered oven at 45°C for 24 hours so that moisture does not accumulate on the seeds. Then the seeds are ground with a grinder and placed in tightly sealed containers until use Tirgar, et al., (2017).

Figure 3. Shows the Removal of Gel from Flax Seeds

Removing fat: Remove the fat (oil) using a Soxhlet device and using hexane solvent for 5 hours, then dry the flax meal .M overnight in an oven at a temperature of 30. Protein isolation from defatted flax meal, Flaxseed protein was extracted according to the method mentioned in (Lan etal, 2020). (By placing flaxseed flour in water at a ratio of (15:1) and adjusting the PH to 8.5 using NaOH with mechanical stirring at 1000 revolutions/minute for 2 hours at Room temperature, then centrifugation is done at 8000 rpm for a period of time, and then the sediment is collected. As for the filtrate, the filtrate is collected and the PH is reduced to the point (IEP). 20 minutes at temperature 4, Then, centrifugation is performed at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes at 4°C, then the sediment is collected and placed in very pure water, and the PH is adjusted to 7 using NaOH, and then the protein is dried, after which the dried protein is ground and packaged in tightly closed plastic containers.

Results and Discussion

We can see in Table 1 the chemical composition of flax protein concentrate, where we notice a decrease in moisture compared to what it was in whole flax seeds to 1.9% due to the use of freeze-drying (lyophilization) technology, and an increase in the protein percentage to 66.58% due the isolation and concentration of the protein that was Obtained by adopting sedimentation at the break-even point. Electrophoresis and the percentage of fat decreased to 1.72% in the protein concentrate of flax due to the removal of fat from the sample using the organic solvent hexane. We also notice from the result that percentage of ash in the protein concentrate increased to 4.8%.

Table 1. Shows the Chemical Composition of Flax Seeds

Moisture	Percentage
	5.07
Protein	26.33
Ash	3.80

Table 2. Shows the Chemical Composition of Flax Protein Concentrate

	Percentage
	1.9
Moisture Protein	66.58
Fat.	4.8
Ash.	1.72

Table 2 shows the ability of flax protein concentrate to form an emulsion, as it was fairly good, 38.33%, while it was.

The emulsion characteristic is affected by several factors, including the size of the fat droplets, the solubility of the protein, and the stability of the emulsion 36.66%. The binary and tertiary structure of proteins, the ratio of the diffuse phase to the continuous phase, ionic and hydrophobic strengths, and viscosity. The product, size and type of other ingredients, as well as the shaking motion of the emulsion. The increase in the amount of dissolved protein that is adsorbed. At the water-oil interface, a greater amount of the fatty part is bound to the water, which is also what Puligundla mentioned (Lim and 2022), where they indicated that there is a direct relationship between solubility and the ability to form an emulsion.

Table 3. Shows the Emulsion Stability of Flax Protein Concentrate

Time/minutes	Water layer	Emulsion layer
0	0	60
5	36	24
15	37	23
45	37	23
60	37	23
90	37	23
120	38	22
180	38	22

Table 3 shows the ability to form foam and stability of flax protein concentrate. The results showed that foam formation.

Foam formation was affected by a factor that was weak (2%) and remained stable throughout the storage period, and the stability of the foam was

(100%). Factors including the protein layer formed at the surface between the liquid and the air, which in turn depends on the extent of protein interactions – Protein and protein-water interactions, and if the protein does not dissolve completely, it is difficult for the protein to form the layer, The temperature, humidity, pH, and concentration, as well as the type of mixer, the mixing method, and the speed and time of mixing., (Lqari etal) One of the factors that has a significant impact on foam capacity and stability. (2005).

Table 4. Shows the Volume of Foam Formed for Flax Protein Concentrate

Tima/minutes	Foam volume
0	2 ml
10	2 ml
30	2 ml
60	2 ml
90	2 ml

The results in Figure 4 show the ability to bind water and fat for the protein center of flax, where

Figure 4. Shows the Ability to Bind Water and Fat of the Flax Protein Concentrate

Conclusion

1. Flax seeds are an important source of protein, as they contain a high percentage of proteins.
2. The method of alkaline extraction and sedimentation at the electrical neutral point was

it was found that the ability to bind water was higher, which reached (2.10 ml water/gm protein) compared to the ability to bind fat, which reached (1.90 ml fat).

gm protein). The increase in the ability to absorb water depends on the great ability of the protein center to swell and open, and then Exposing new binding sites. The ability to bind fat is due to the difference in the proportion of hydrophobic amino acids, i.e.

Polarity on the surface of the protein molecule, where the non-polar side chains of the protein serve to connect the chains Hydrocarbon, thus the fat is retained inside the protein molecule because the protein contains non-covalent bonds

Such as hydrophobic forces and electrostatic forces, which contribute to increasing the absorption of fat, and many researchers have recorded

The ability to absorb fat varies depending on the hydrophobic ability of the protein, as well as the shape of the protein.

more efficient and better in isolating and concentrating, Flaxseed proteins.

3. The foam stability of the flax protein concentrate was better than the capacity of the foam formed.

4. The protein concentrate of flax has fairly good emulsifying properties.
5. The protein concentrate of flax has good water and fat binding properties.

Recommendations

1. The possibility of using flax protein concentrate as a good protein source that can be used to fortify some foods.
2. Trying to introduce protein concentrates into food applications in the future due to their good functional properties and value.
3. Study more functional properties of flax protein concentrate.
4. Producing protein hydrolysates rich in peptides with small molecular weights and using them as antioxidants or .Bioactive peptides

References

- AOAC. (1980). *Official methods of analysis* (13th ed.). Association of Official Analytical Chemists.
- De Lourdes, R., & Giada, M. (2010). Food applications for flaxseed and its components: Products and processing. *Recent Patents on Food, Nutrition & Agriculture*, 2, 181–186.
- EL-Jasser, A. S. H. (2010). Chemical and biological properties of local cowpea seed protein grown in Gizan region. *International Journal of Applied and Basic Sciences*, 1(2).
- Fale, S. K., Umekar, M. J., Das, R., & Alaspur, M. (2022). A comprehensive study of herbal cosmetics prepared from flaxseed. *Multidisciplinary International Research Journal of Gujarat Technological University*, 4, 106–112.
- Hindi, M. J. (1979). *The recovery of functional protein from fish waste* (Ph.D. thesis). Loughborough University of Technology, England.
- Jasim, M. A. (1983). *Functional plastein from fish waste* (Ph.D. thesis). Loughborough University of Technology, England.
- Joslyn, M. A. (1970). *Method in food analysis*. Academic Press.
- Khalid, E. K., Babiker, E. E., & Tinay, A. H. (2003). Solubility and functionality properties of sesame seed proteins as influenced by pH and/or salt concentration. *Food Chemistry*, 361-366.
- Lan, Y., Ohm, J. B., Chen, B., & Rao, J. (2020). Physicochemical properties and profiles of flaxseed aroma proteins extracted from whole flaxseed and flaxseed meal. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 104, 105731.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2020.105731>
- Lqari, H., Pedroche, J., Giron-Calle, J., Vioque, J., & Millan, F. (2005). Production of *Lupinus angustifolius* protein hydrolysates with improved functional properties. *Grasas y Aceites*, 56(2).
- Mao, X., & Hua, Y. (2012). Composition, structure and functional properties of protein concentrates and isolates produced from walnut (*Juglans regia* L.). *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 13, 1561-1581.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms13021561>
- Martinez-Flores, H. E., Soto, E. B., Garinca-Romo, M. G., Saldana, A. L., & Penagos, C. J. C. (2013). Chemical and functional properties of flaxseed protein concentrate obtained using surface response methodology. *Food Chemistry*, 106, 1166-1174.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2013.09.003>
- Moongngarm, A., Sasanam, S., Pinsiri, W., Inthasoi, P., Janto, S., & Pengchai, J. (2014). Functional properties of protein concentrate from black cowpea and its application. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 11(10), 1811-1818.
- Mueed, A., Shibli, S., Korma, S. A., Madjirebaye, P., Esatbeyoglu, T., & Deng, Z. (2022). Flaxseed bioactive compounds: chemical composition, functional properties, food applications and health benefits-related gut microbes. *Foods*, 11(20), 3307.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11203307>

Pearson, D. (1971). *The chemical analysis of foods* (6th ed.). Chemical Publishing Co., Inc.

Puligundla, P., & Lim, S. (2022). A review of extraction techniques and food applications of flaxseed mucilage. *Foods*, *11*, 1677. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11111677>

Saka, y., Baumgartner, B., & Özkaya, B. (2022). Usability of microfluidized flaxseed as a functional additive in bread. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, *102*, 505–513. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.11378>

Sanmartin, C., Taglieri, I., Venturi, F., Macaluso, M., Zinnai, A., Tavarini, S., Botto, A., Serra, A., Conte, G., & Flamini, G. (2020). Flaxseed cake as a tool for the improvement of nutraceutical and sensorial features of sourdough bread. *Foods*, *9*, 204. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9020204>

Taha, F. S., Mohamed, S. S., Wagdy, S. M., & Mohmad, G. F. (2013). Antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of enzymatic hydrolysis products from sunflower protein isolate. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, *21*(5), 651-658.

Tirgar, M., Silcock, P., Carne, A., & Birch, E. J. (2017). Effect of extraction method on functional properties of flaxseed protein concentrates. *Food Chemistry*, *215*, 417-424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.07.164>

Wu, S., Wang, X., Qi, W., & Guo, Q. (2019). Bioactive protein/peptides of flaxseed: A review. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, *92*, 184–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2019.08.013>